

NOTES

concentration of HNO_3 increases. It is interesting to note that for 15 and 30 min durations, in the presence of 0.2% meta nitroaniline, the loss in weight of 70/30 brass in 3.0N nitric acid is slightly less than that in 2.0N nitric acid. In the presence of meta nitroaniline the potential values with time are more negative than those in its absence indicating its action on the local cathodes. Addition of meta nitroaniline induces a significant increase in the cathode polarisation.

Conclusions: All the substances are satisfactory inhibitors for the corrosion of 70/30 brass in the nitric acid. The order of efficiency is m-nitroaniline > m-chloroaniline > m-anisidine > m-toluidine.

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Interaction of Yttrium(III), Lanthanum(III), Cerium(III) and Uranium(VI) with Salicyloyl-hydrazide.

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THE chelating behaviour of salicyloyl-hydrazide with Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Mg^{2+} , has been reported by Jabalpurwala and co-workers¹. The present paper describes the results of potentiometric titration studies on Y^{3+} , La^{3+} , Ce^{3+} and UO_2^{2+} chelates of salicyloyl-hydrazide in water dioxane mixture at ionic strengths of 0.01, 0.05, 0.10 and 0.15M.

Experimental

Salicyloyl-hydrazide was prepared by the known method². Due to the limited solubility of the ligand in water, pH titration studies were carried out in 50% water dioxane mixture. In the case of Ce^{3+} , 25:75 water-dioxane mixture was used due to precipitation in 50% water dioxane mixture. Solutions of potassium nitrate and nitric acid were used to maintain the ionic strengths. The titrations were carried out at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ using Calvin-Bjerrum^{3,4} technique as used by Irving and Rossotti⁵. The following solutions (total volumes 20 ml in each case) were titrated against standard KOH solution; A) (2 ml of 0.01M HNO_3 ; B) (A + 2 ml of 0.05M ligand; C) B + 2 ml of 0.01M metal ion. Since the pH titrations were carried out in water dioxane medium, appropriate corrections as per Van Uitert and Hass⁶ was applied.

Results and Discussion

The values of $\log K_1^H$ at the various ionic concentrations are reported in Table 1. The formation curves (Fig. 1.) extend between $\bar{n}=0$ and $\bar{n}=3$ for La^{3+} , Y^{3+}

FIG. 1 FORMATION CURVES OF SALICYLOYLHYDRAZIDE CHELATES

chelates and $\bar{n}=0$ and $\bar{n}=2$ in the case of UO_2^{2+} and Ce^{3+} chelates. It is observed that UO_2^{2+} forms chelates of 1:2 composition in the pH range 3.20-6.25, while the same stoichiometry is obtained for Ce^{3+} chelates in the pH range 5.00-7.50. It has also been observed that La^{3+} and Y^{3+} form three types of chelates in the ratio of 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 in the pH range 6.00-8.75 and 5.00-8.00 respectively.

The values of stability constants were obtained by interpolation at half \bar{n} values⁷. The values of $\log K_2$ and overall stability constants, $\log \beta_2$ of 1:2 chelates of UO_2^{2+} , were obtained from Fig. 1, using the following relations.

$$\log K_2 = (\text{pL})\bar{n} = 1.5$$

$$\log \beta_2 = 2(\text{pL})\bar{n} = 1.0$$

The formation curve for UO_2^{2+} system starts at the value above $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and, therefore, the $\log K_1$ values for this system were obtained as difference.

$$\log K_1 = \log \beta_2 - \log K_2.$$

The metal-ligand stability data at various μ values (Table 1.) reveal that values of $\log K_1/K_2$ and $\log K_2/K_3$ are positive and $\log \beta_2$ values suggest that with an increase in the ionic strength of the medium the values of stability constants of La^{3+} , Y^{3+} and UO_2^{2+} chelates with salicyloyl-hydrazide decrease. According to Huckel⁸ the activity of the metal ion for its interaction with other molecular species varies inversely as the ionic strength of the medium in which the reactions were studied. On this basis, the decrease in stabilities for salicyloyl-hydrazide chelates of Y^{3+} , La^{3+} and UO_2^{2+} in solutions of increasing ionic strength is justified which is also in agreement with the results obtained by the authors⁹ for La^{3+} complexes.

The observed stability order $\text{UO}_2^{2+} > \text{Y}^{3+} > \text{La}^{3+}$ for $\log \beta_n$ values is justified on the basis of Z^2/r values for these metal ions which are in the sequence given above. The $\log \beta_n$ values for cerium complexes are less as compared with those of Y^{3+} , La^{3+} and UO_2^{2+} ions. Since in the case of Ce^{3+} , the reaction has been studied in 25:75 (v/v) water dioxane mixture, the medium being less polar it indicates that the product formed is more polar and therefore it precipitates due to

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SALICYLOYL-HYDRAZIDE CHELATES AT 35°

Cation	Medium H ₂ O : dioxane	Ionic strength	Log K ₁	Log K ₂	Log K ₃	Log β _n
H ⁺	50:50	0.01	9.10	—	—	9.10
		0.05	9.07	—	—	9.07
		0.10	9.05	—	—	9.05
		0.15	9.03	—	—	9.03
UO ₂ ²⁺	50:50	0.01	8.76	6.20	—	14.96
		0.05	8.64	6.16	—	14.80
		0.10	8.42	6.30	—	14.72
		0.15	8.12	6.20	—	14.32
Y ³⁺	50:50	0.01	5.93	5.20	4.23	15.36
		0.05	5.45	4.80	4.02	14.27
		0.10	5.40	4.75	4.00	14.15
		0.15	5.10	4.46	3.82	13.38
La ³⁺	50:50	0.01	5.06	4.19	3.56	12.18
		0.05	4.50	3.72	3.14	11.36
		0.10	4.58	3.68	3.06	11.32
		0.15	4.43	3.54	3.05	11.07
Ce ³⁺	25:75	0.01	5.40	4.54	—	9.94
		0.05	5.18	4.44	—	9.62
		0.10	5.28	4.54	—	9.82
		0.15	5.16	4.72	—	9.88

decreased solubility. The extent of association of ions decreases more in the case of Ce³⁺ as compared to Y³⁺, La³⁺ and UO₂²⁺. Accordingly this accounts for the lower stability of cerium complexes.

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Chalcones XIV : Potential Germicides Derived From Acetyl Naphthalene

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DURING recent years many homocyclic¹⁻⁶, and heterocyclic^{8,14} chalcone analogues have been reported to possess bactericidal, fungicidal, germicidal^{9,10}, analgesic¹¹, antiinflammatory, sedative¹¹ carcinogenic⁷, etc. activity. Marked bactericidal⁷ activity is exhibited by naphthalene, phenanthrene chalcones

and also by 2-furfurylidene acetophenone and 2-thienyl styryl⁸ ketones. These observations have prompted us to synthesise naphthyl chalcones. This paper is in continuation^{4-6,9,10,13,14} of our programme to study the structure activity relationship of 2-naphthyl chalcones as potential germicides.

In view of the well known physiological activity of phenanthrene and anthracene chalcones it was thought desirable to synthesise nineteen naphthyl chalcones with the expectation of enhanced activity. Also, that naphthalene compounds are easily scattered over the system owing to its increased lipid solubility and, therefore, a good contact with the disease germs is possible.

The compounds were synthesised by condensation of 2-acetylnaphthalene with substituted benzaldehydes according to the general procedure described earlier⁶. The condensation of 2-acetonaphthone with chloro-, methyl-, and methoxy benzaldehydes gave well crystalline products with 25% alcoholic caustic potash solution at room temperature within 24 to 36 hrs. whereas the condensation with hydroxy benzaldehydes under these conditions produced only viscous tarry masses from which no crystalline compound could be obtained. It may be due to resinification and other side reactions of hydroxy benzaldehydes with concentrated alkali solution. It is interesting to note that condensation of 2-acetonaphthone with nitrobenzaldehydes in presence of the same concentration of alkali solution gave immediately dark coloured compounds of unknown composition, whereas condensation at low temperature (10°-15°) with 5% alkali solution produced well crystalline yellow compounds.

The compounds thus synthesised are listed in Table 1 and are characterised by their physical properties, halochromism with concentrated sulphuric acid, by preparing 2 : 4-DNPS of a few compounds and elemental analyses. The analyses of the elements (Table 1) were within ±0.5% of the theoretical value. All melting points are uncorrected.

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